

A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF THE TYPES OF QUESTIONS USED BY TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

A teacher's art of questioning is proven essential in any aspect of education. It only differs as to what kind of question is being asked – LOTS or HOTS questions that enhance students' thinking skills. This study aims to examine the source, methodological characteristics, findings, and recommendations of the studies. This study followed the PRISMA guidelines for conducting systematic reviews. It included an analysis of 16 studies extracted from three electronic databases, ranging from fifteen years late to the currency of the study. The results show that teachers' questioning: 1) questioning is effective in cultivating students' skills; 2) they are more likely to use LOTS than HOTS; and 3) regular professional development is a need for teachers that will sustain their skills in implementing HOT questioning. Concerning the results, it is crucial to develop both pre-service and in-service teachers' skills in questioning.

Keywords: *Questioning skills; Skill; Higher-order thinking skill; Lower-order thinking skill; Question type*

INTRODUCTION

In education, the art of questioning is extremely vital. (Wilén and Swartz, 2017; and Neta, 2019). It is an essential skill that all teachers should possess to effectively foster critical thinking abilities in their students (Warren and Hughes, 2018). This multifaceted ability centers on the capability to articulate challenging questions that drive students to go

beyond the obvious and reveal deeper levels of understanding for a variety of subjects. Teachers can fashion a learning environment that nurtures rational curiosity and hastens cognitive growth (Çalık & Aksu, 2018) by encouraging students to analyze, synthesize, and evaluate information more profoundly. This emphasis on asking questions has become more and more prominent in the educational setting since it is recognized to play a critical role in shaping the minds of the future's innovators and leaders (Caine et al., 2015; Walsh & Sattes, 2015). The capacity to ask insightful questions benefits students, encourages them to engage with the material at a deeper level, and develops a mindset that views inquiry as an essential part of learning. This gives students the skills they need to deal with complexity and exercise critical thought in a world that is constantly changing. The development of effective questioning techniques is essential for equipping students to become lifelong learners who can navigate the complex terrain of intellectual inquiry and knowledge acquisition as the educational landscape changes.

The teacher asking questions, enhances professional growth as teachers continuously reflect on their practice, refine instructional strategies, and develop a deeper understanding of the subject matter (National Research Council, 2012), promotes creativity and innovation, and teachers have the opportunity to explore creative teaching approaches, adapt curriculum materials and design innovatively that caters to the needs of the diverse students (Harlen & Qualter, 2017), asking question empower the teacher improves classroom management by leading and setting the class to fruitful discussion and good environment increases job satisfaction and teachers' efficacy (Fullan & Hargreaves, 2016)

The practice of questioning within educational contexts finds its roots in the profound and philosophical teachings of the ancient Greek philosopher Socrates, who championed the Socratic method as a way to cultivate critical thinking skills through the careful crafting of questions (Chen, H., & Wu, T., 2020; Wang, Y., & Lin, S., 2015). This method, which places a strong emphasis on the power of inquiry and dialogue, has served as a cornerstone in the realm of pedagogy for centuries. Though it was not until the turn of the 20th century that researchers and educators organized a systematic investigation of the complex character of questions and their significant impact on teachers' and students' learning.

This academic excursion into the area of questioning unveiled a variety of diverse question types, bearing exceptional potential to shape and revitalize student learning experiences. Therefore, this academic journey illuminated the profound importance of crafting and positioning questions purposefully as an indispensable tool in the educational arsenal (Schoenfeld, 2017; McNeill & Krajcik, 2019; Berg & Smith, 2016; Kaminski & Sloutsky, 2020). With its development over time, questioning has become more than just a teaching technique; it is now considered a fundamental component of successful teaching strategies. The intricate relationship between questions and learning objectives has paved the standing of questioning as an essential component of educational praxis, enhancing the variety of instructional approaches and opening up new avenues for intellectual exploration for teachers and students alike. Educators can customize the transformative power of this age-old yet always-evolving educational method to kindle

intellectual discourse, nurture curiosity, and promote a culture of lifelong learning in educational settings by welcoming the art of questioning with open arms and smart discernment.

In today's fast-paced and information-driven society, students are always bombarded with an overwhelming quantity of data from a variety of sources, including online platforms, traditional media outlets, and academic resources (Chen & Liu, 2017). Despite the abundance of information available, countless students struggle to effectively analyze, evaluate, and apply it. This dilemma draws attention to a critical problem in modern education: students often discover it difficult to obtain the essential capabilities needed for critical thinking in an environment full of varied information. In today's world, where false information and fake news are hardly spotted, the capacity to evaluate information critically, recognize biases, and reach well-informed conclusions is becoming more and more important. Thus, it is more important than ever for educators to give students' development of critical thinking skills the highest importance.

Given these challenges, teachers play a crucial role in both imparting knowledge and helping students develop their critical thinking skills. Collins & Duguid (2003) found that through their studies, teachers can encourage students to question, explore, and think for themselves by fostering a stimulating and supportive learning environment. Teachers can help students become knowledgeable and involved members of the information environment by implementing dynamic teaching strategies like Socratic questioning, critical reading exercises, and problem-based learning. Critical thinking instruction also equips students with the abilities necessary to handle challenging circumstances, make informed choices, and adapt to society's rapid changes. Through nurturing a mindset that values logical thinking, fact-based reasoning, and innovative approaches to problem-solving, educators contribute to shaping a cohort of individuals prepared to face the demands of the 21st century.

Also, asking questions is only one aspect of the art of questioning; there is much more to it. It involves the deft application of a variety of question forms, such as open-ended questions that promote in-depth contemplation, probing questions that explore underlying presumptions, and follow-up questions that guide students in the development of critical thinking abilities (Cheng, K., & Chan, W., 2019). Teachers are entrusted with the duty of identifying the subtle range of questioning levels, from simple factual queries to sophisticated analytical challenges, and they need to strategically apply each type to pique students' intellectual curiosity and promote cognitive development.

Teachers are able to involve students in meaningful dialogues that encourage them to explore ideas, clarify concepts, and gain a deeper understanding of the subject by skillfully incorporating a variety of question types and levels of complexity into classroom discussions. This method of instruction fosters a classroom culture that values diversity, celebrates curiosity, and encourages students' ongoing intellectual growth, as well as developing their ability to think independently and solve problems.

As education evolves, the art of questioning will remain an important component in developing a generation of learners who are prepared to navigate an ever-changing world. With the necessity and significance of placing a high priority on helping students develop their critical thinking abilities through engaging instructional techniques and the thoughtful application of varying degrees of questioning to spark intellectual curiosity and promote a diverse and curious classroom environment, this study will attempt to identify the source and methodological characteristics of the studies, analyze the findings and recommendations of the studies, and find out what are the common types of questions used by the teachers in the classroom and what are their recommendations for teachers.

Research questions

- 1) What are the common types of questions used by the teachers in the classroom?
- 2) What are the studies' recommendations for teachers?

METHODOLOGY

Data Sources

A comprehensive literature review was done following the PRISMA guidelines, examining the studies directly or indirectly. The steps taken are: 1) have the initial screening of titles and abstracts to identify potentially relevant studies; 2) review the full text of the potentially relevant studies to determine their eligibility for inclusion; 3) extract the relevant data from included studies; 4) evaluate and synthesize the data from included studies; and finally, report the findings of the systematic review. The keywords were "teacher questioning," "questioning skills," "questioning," and "questioning techniques." Regarding the inclusion and exclusion criteria, 16 studies were found to be eligible to explore teachers' art of questioning. The data reduction chart for this systematic review is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Data abatement chart for Systematic Review

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Methodological characteristics of the studies

Among all the research, Indonesia has the most articles with 62.5%, followed by Malaysia, Thailand, Pakistan, the United Kingdom, the US, Turkey, and Iran with 6.25% each. As

for the methodological characteristics of the studies, 50.00% used a qualitative, 31.25% used a quantitative, and 18.75% used a mixed methodology (Table 1).

Table 1: Methodological characteristics of the studies

Authors	Research	Methodology	participants	Country
Ansori, 2019	Quantitative	Survey	15 English teachers	Surakarta, Indonesia.
Shalihin, et.al., 2019	Quantitative	Quasi-experimental	30 participants were students	Indonesia
Rahmi, et. al., 2019	Quantitative	quasi-experimental design	32 students	Padang, Indonesia
Mitarlis, et.al., 2020	Quantitative	Quasi-experimental	59 participants	Bontang, Indonesia,
Hill, 2016	Quantitative	Quasi-experimental	Participants are not specified	Southern Thailand
Sujariati, et.al., 2016	Qualitative	Discourse analysis	4 English teachers	SMAN Bontomarannu, State University of Makassar in Indonesia
Tyas, et.al., 2019	Qualitative	Not specified	18 in-service teachers	Central Java and East Java, Indonesia
Khan, et.al., 2011	Qualitative	Observation	20 teachers	Peshawar, Pakistan,
Harrop, et.al, 2010	Qualitative	Interview	10 teachers in infant schools, 10 in junior schools and 10 in secondary schools	Liverpool, UK
Seker, et.al., 2008	Qualitative	Structured interview	15 English Language Teaching	Mugla University, Turkey
Barjesteh, et.al., 2014	Qualitative	Observation	30 Iranian students at a private English institute	Amol, Iran
Tofade, et.al., 2013	Qualitative	Observation	91 faculty members	Maryland, United States
Rooney, 2012	Qualitative	Action research	1 teacher	Surakarta, Indonesia

Gozali,et.al., 2021	Mixed method	Case study	15 secondary teachers	Indonesia
Shafeei, et.al., 2017	Mixed- methods	observations, interviews, and questionnaires	12 English secondary school teachers were the respondents	Malaysia
Djami, et.al., 2019	Mixed method	case study	15 teachers'	Salatiga

- a) Qualitative studies. Of the sixteen studies, 50.00% used a qualitative. The characteristic of this qualitative approach is that it focuses on exploring and understanding complex phenomena through an in-depth examination of subjective experiences, meanings, and perspectives (Creswell & Poth, 2017). This involves collecting data through methods such as 1) action research (Rooney, 2012); and 2) the study focused on inquiry-based learning (IBL), which is a student-centered approach that encourages learners to construct new ideas based on their experiences and prior knowledge. It also emphasizes the importance of problem-solving, inferring, estimating, predicting, generalizing, and creative thinking as higher-order thinking skills, highlighting the significance of developing these skills for students' educational success and their ability to navigate a complex and evolving world. 2) Observation: Tofade et al.'s (2013)' study emphasizes the use of questions as a teaching tool to improve learning outcomes. It highlights the importance of well-constructed questions in assessing knowledge, promoting comprehension, and stimulating critical thinking, Barjesteh, et.al., (2014), the study highlights the importance of teacher questions and questioning strategies in an EFL classroom in Iran, and for Khan, et.al., (2011), the study brought the issue of questioning to the forefront, the common order of questions that teachers ask in the classrooms, and better strategies to improve higher-order thinking skills through questioning; 3) Discourse analysis of Sujariati, et.al., (2016), the study highlighted the importance of various types of questions, questioning frequency, techniques, and student engagement and the use of wait time, repeated questions, translation into Bahasa dialect, clarity, close approach, and rewards for correct answers; 4) (Structured) Interview of Seker, et.al., (2008) focuses on the relationship between critical thinking skills and in-class questioning behaviors of English Language Teaching (ELT) students and the differences in questioning behaviors between students with higher and lower critical thinking scores, emphasizing the importance of developing critical thinking skills in teacher education to prepare students for thoughtful and analytical learning experiences, as for Harrop, et.al, (2010) it focuses on a variety of question types that teachers use, such as routine, task-supervision, open-ended, and closed-ended inquiries and stressed on how crucial it is to pose relevant questions because doing so has an impact on students' engagement and learning. The intricacy of questions from elementary, middle, and high schools was also investigated in this study.

b) There were 31.25% who used a quantitative study. The characteristics of quantitative research include its emphasis on numerical analysis and objective measurement to investigate phenomena (Sanders, 2019). This includes 1) a survey study by Ansori (2019) that focuses on the significance of effective questioning in fostering higher-order thinking skills in students. It uses Bloom's Taxonomy to classify cognitive processes in educational settings, ranging from simple recall to complex evaluation, synthesis, and analysis. Also points out that teachers should develop students' critical thinking dispositions through metacognitive techniques, interactive teaching techniques, and problem-based learning; 2) Quasi-experimental of Shalihin et al. (2019) that highlights the use of guided inquiry learning to improve students' critical thinking skills in aspects such as elementary clarification, basic support, inference, advanced clarification, and strategies and tactics; Rahmi et al. al. (2019), that emphasizes the importance of inquiry-based learning in enhancing students' critical thinking skills; Mitarlis et al. (2020), focused on assessing the effectiveness of open inquiry with multiple representation approaches in enhancing students' critical thinking skills in electrochemistry education; and Hill (2016) focused on the higher-level questions, the nature of the questions asked by teachers, and the importance of teacher training and professional development in understanding the importance of questioning techniques.

c) There were 18.75% who used the mixed method. This study enables the researchers to gain a deeper and broader understanding of what is under investigation (Teddlie & Tashakkori, 2009), as well as triangulation (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017). This approach was employed by Gozali et al. (2021) that highlights the importance of understanding how language teachers engage with and perceive HOTS questioning, the impact of HOTS questioning on language learning, and the efficacy of language teachers in encouraging the development of critical thinking skills among students; Shafeei et al. (2017) point out the relevance of higher-order thinking skills (HOTS) to improving students' critical thinking skills; and Djami et al. (2019).

B. Findings of the Studies

Of the studies analyzed, only 11 from different countries found that teachers are settling on LOTS questions for some reason (Table 2). This is supported by the studies of Bloom (1956) and Cooper, et al. (2019). Some studies found that teachers typically center their questions on factual information rather than prioritizing questions that develop higher-order thinking skills in students, just like the study of Snyder & Snyder (2008), Klieme, et al. (2004), Oliver & Reschly (2007).

Table 2: Teachers' categorization of question usage

Authors	Result	
	LOTS	HOTS
Barjesteh, et.al., 2014	✓	
Djami, et.al., 2019		✓
Harrop, et.al, 2010	✓	

Hill, 2016	✓
Khan, et.al., 2011	✓
Mitarlis, et.al., 2020	✓
Rahmi, et. al., 2019	✓
Seker, et, al., 2008	✓
Shafeei, et.al., 2017	✓
Sujariati, et.al., 2016	✓
Tofade, et.al., 2013	✓

On the other hand, the other five studies included in the analysis showed a different result from Table 1. Only 12.5% showed its effectiveness to the student, as was discussed in the study of Rooney (2012) and Shalihin, et al. (2019). They proved that HOTS questioning or HOTS inquiry-based teaching is effective for students, and teachers are deliberately acquainted with the skill. It is also reiterated in the study of Rooney (2012) that HOT-based questions are engaging if the process is deliberately discussed with the students, making them informed and aware of the skill and process. The other 12.5% of the study proved that teachers are settling for LOTS due to the students' lack of proficiency and understanding, which leads to teachers just resolving to use LOTS (Bloom, 1956; Graesser et al., 1995; Hattie, 2009). That is shown in the study of Gozali (2021) and the study of Tyas, et al. (2019), which proved that if teachers are not acquainted with and do not have experience with the HOTS skill, it will reflect the questions used in teaching. Finally, Ansori (2019) discovered that at some point during the lecture, students ask HOT questions out of curiosity rather than to gain a thorough understanding of the material. His study also demonstrated that teachers have strong self-efficacy in terms of HOTS. See Table 3.

Table 3: Descriptive findings of the study

Author	Result of the Study
Rooney, 2012	Students engaged in the inquiry-based learning process
Shalihin, et.al., 2019	Students demonstrated a higher improvement when the HOT was discussed and implemented.
Tyas, et.al., 2019	The data analysis identified three main challenges: teachers' limited understanding of HOTS, limited experience in developing HOTS-based assessments, teaching and learning resources, and students' heterogeneity in cognitive competence, resulting in difficulty in developing appropriate instructions
Gozali, et.al., 2021	The student's proficiency is a hurdle in using HOT questions and English and language medium might be an important factor affecting the abilities of teachers to ask HOT questions
Ansori, 2019	Students ask HOT queries out of fascination.

English teachers are confident in their ability to use interactive, critical thinking, and metacognitive pedagogical strategies to promote HOTS during the learning process.

Aside from what is identified by Rooney and Tyas as the prevalence of LOTS, there are other factors underlying the occurrence of lower-order thinking skills (LOTS) in teachers' questioning, which is a complex issue influenced by several underlying factors. The first significant factor is the traditional emphasis on repetitive learning and standardized testing in many educational systems. This emphasis on memorization and recall of factual knowledge unintentionally promotes LOTS, in which students are instructed to bring up information rather than engage in critical thinking. Second, teachers' pedagogical knowledge and beliefs are critical. Those who do not have a thorough understanding of higher-order thinking skills (HOTS) may struggle to develop questions that encourage critical analysis, problem-solving, and creativity in students (Chin and Chia, 2017). Third, limited time and large class sizes (Tyas, 2019) can limit teachers' ability to conduct extensive questioning. The pressure to cover massive amounts of curriculum competencies / content frequently causes teachers to prioritize LOTS, which require less cognitive effort from students and can be answered more quickly (Clarke & Yore, 2010). Finally, teachers' workloads and stress levels can have an impact on their questioning strategies. High levels of stress and exhaustion may make it difficult for teachers to invest in the cognitive resources needed for HOTS questioning, leading to a LOTS default (Van de Griff, 2016). Therefore, addressing the prevalence of LOTS in teachers' questioning requires a multifaceted approach that includes curriculum reform, professional development for teachers, and the creation of supportive classroom environments.

Recommendation of the studies

This section provides some study recommendations that can serve as a starting point for future research. 75% (Table 4) of the study suggested that teachers undergo professional development that supports their understanding of HOTS and how to conceptualize questions and utilize them in class.

To improve student outcomes, educators must stay up-to-date on research and best practices, provide feedback, and provide adequate support, as well as provide opportunities for teachers to engage in learning activities similar to those they will use with their students. Engaging in professional growth workshops, conferences, and online courses enables teachers to assist students in building these abilities. Research indicates (Darling-Hammond, et al., 2017; Learning Forward, 2011; National Council of Teachers of Mathematics, 2014) that pursuing professional development has beneficial effects on student achievement and engagement, which renders it an excellent investment for teachers. This professional development should also focus on updating teachers' knowledge, skills, and approaches in light of new teaching trends that enable teachers to apply changes to curricula and teaching practices. Thus, this development is not only limited to formal courses but can also be a collaboration between schools or teachers across schools.

Table 4: Studies' Recommendation

Authors	Recommendations					
	Further / continuous training or professional development	Translating English question to dialect	Use varied questioning strategies	Interactive learning exercises	Balance the teaching style of questions	Did not offer a recommendation
Ansori, 2019	✓					
Barjesteh, et.al., 2014	✓					
Djami, et.al., 2019	✓					
Gozali, et.al., 2021	✓					
Harrop, et.al, 2010						✓
Hill, 2016			✓			
Khan, et.al., 2011					✓	
Mitarlis, et.al., 2020	✓					
Rahmi, et. al., 2019				✓		
Rooney, 2012						✓
Seker, et.al., 2008			✓			
Shafeei, et.al., 2017	✓					
Shalihin, et.al., 2019			✓			
Sujariati, et.al., 2016		✓				
Tofade, et.al., 2013						✓
Tyas, et.al., 2019	✓					
	43.75	6.25	18.75	6.25	6.25	18.75

1.1. There were 18.75% recommended using varied questioning strategies in class. The strategies are open-ended questions, probing questions, hypothetical questions, reflective questions, choice questions, clarification questions, comparison questions, sequencing questions, summarizing questions, and higher-order questioning.

1.2. Open-ended questions are questions that are answered by elaboration. These questions encourage students to provide more detailed answers, express opinions, and share experiences. These questions are beneficial in various contexts, such as they promote deep thinking, encourage detailed responses, and help gather in-depth data from the students. Some of the examples of open-ended questions in English language arts subject are:

- a. What did you find interesting about the main character of the story?

- b. Explain how the setting of the story is influenced by the plot development.
 - c. What connections can you make between the events of the story and your own life experience?
 - d. In your opinion, what was the purpose of the author in writing the story?
- 1.3. Clarification questions are simple factual questions that aim to clarify information that was initially provided by the student and provide essential details. Some of the examples are
- a. Can you clarify what you mean by the author's use of imagery in the story?
 - b. Could provide a more specific example of how the protagonist can champion the struggle he is facing?
 - c. Can you explain more in detail how the setting is being influenced by the development of the story?
 - d. I want to make sure I understand – did the author use foreshadowing to hint who will be the antagonist of the story?
- 1.4. Comparison questions involve analyzing the similarities and differences between two or more subjects or topics. In the context of language arts subjects, comparison questions can be based on literature, language, and communications, and alike. Some examples are:
- a. Compare and contrast the use of symbolism in the story Macbeth and Iliad.
 - b. Discuss the narrative styles of two poets, Emily Dickinson and Langston Hughes.
 - c. Examine how the portrayal of female characters in classic versus contemporary literature is.
 - d. Compare the effectiveness of dialogue in play and screenplay.
- 1.5. Sequencing questions are questions that involve the organization or chronological of events or steps logically. This sequencing question is very much applicable to other subjects just like performing science experiments wherein students will sequentially practice the steps in conducting investigations effectively to understand the process. In language art subject this is most applicable to story, for instance:
- a. What happened in the first part of the story?
 - b. Describe the sequence of the climax and how the conflict resolves.
 - c. Can you retell the story in chronological order?
 - d. Who are the characters presented in the story according to their order and characteristics?
- 1.6. Sequential questions are questions in a progression manner from LOTS to HOTS depending on the subject matter and strategies in asking questions and this is another term for balanced questioning. This strategy is effective since it is a structured/patterned order that helps create a psychologically safe environment by starting with LOTS questions before progressing to HOTS which promotes students' involvement and interest.

- 1.7. Summarizing questions are designed to test a student's ability to condense and articulate the main ideas of a text concisely. These questions required students to identify key elements and extract important points using their own words. This helps the students develop their HOT skills, memory retention, and comprehension and extract key points for better understanding across subjects. Some examples are
- a. Can you provide a brief overview of the main theme of the story?
 - b. What are the key elements that drive the plot forward?
 - c. What is the main style technique of the author?
 - d. Can you summarize the tension in the story?
- 1.8. Higher-order questioning refers to questions that require critical thinking, such as analysis, synthesis, and evaluation, rather than just recalling factual information. This prompts deeper engagement and understanding of the subject matter. These question types encourage students to think critically, make connections, and develop their ideas. The examples are:
- a. How does the author use symbolism to convey a deeper meaning in the text?
 - b. Can you evaluate the effectiveness of the protagonist's decisions and actions within the context of the story?
 - c. How does the setting of the story contribute to the overall message of the story?
 - d. Can you propose an alternative ending based on your interpretation of the text?

By incorporating a range of questioning techniques in the classroom, educators can better engage students and promote a more interactive and dynamic learning environment. This can lead to enhanced critical thinking skills and a deeper understanding of the subject matter.

Moreover, varied questioning techniques can cater to the diverse learning styles and preferences of students (Smith & Johnson, 2018; Garcia & Fernandez, 2017; Patel & Sharma, 2020). By using a mix of questioning techniques, educators can cater to the individual needs of their students and ensure that everyone can participate and engage with the material in a meaningful way.

The study by Rahmi et al. (2019), has recommended that the art of questioning be studied through interactive learning exercises. Interactive learning exercises are activities or tasks designed to engage students in a participatory, collaborative, and hands-on learning experience. These exercises encourage students to actively participate in the learning process rather than passively receiving information. Interactive learning exercises can take various forms, such as group discussions, problem-solving activities, simulations, role-plays, and multimedia-based activities. See Table 5 for sample questions.

Table 5: Interactive Learning Activities and Sample Questions

Interactive Learning Activities	Sample Questions
Discussions	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Can you propose an alternative solution based on the groups' discussion? 2. What criteria would you use to judge the project? 3. How do you interpret the main theme of the text?
Problem-solving activities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How does the characters' problem contribute to the story's conflict? 2. How can you use the evidence in the story to support your justification of the characters' actions? 3. How does the cultural background of the character influence the interactions and decisions?
Simulations	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How can you negotiate a conflict between two characters based on their personalities? 2. As a character in the story, what decision would you make differently and how would this alter the story plot? 3. How does your interpretation of the story differ from the other?
Role-plays	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How can you justify your character's action considering his motivations? 2. What are some potential consequences of your actions if you say yes to his evil plans? 3. How would you react if I am not going to appear in the climax?
Multimedia-based activities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How effective does the television presentation capture the theme and motif of the text? 2. What social media post and platform would you be doing if the song is about a mother's love? 3. How are you going to strategize cohesion while working on your online role-play?

Smith & Brown (2018) and Johnson & White (2017) proved that interactive learning exercises enhance student engagement, motivation, and critical thinking skills. They encourage group work, collaboration, and communication, preparing students for real-life situations. These exercises cater to diverse learning styles, allowing students to engage in hands-on activities, discussions, and multimedia-based tasks. They encourage self-directed learning, allowing students to take ownership of their learning process. Active participation in interactive learning exercises improves knowledge retention and application, preparing students for real-world situations.

Khan et al. (2011), with a percentage of 6.25%, proposed that teachers balance their question-based teaching styles. According to the study's findings, out of 267 questions, 67% were knowledge-based, 23% comprehension-based, 7% application-based, 2%

analysis-based, and 1% synthesis-based. However, the ratio of evaluation-based questions was zero.

- 1) A balance of lower-order thinking skills (LOTS) and higher-order thinking skills (HOTS) questions in class is required for a variety of reasons. The NEA (2016) and Tomlinson (2014) highlight the importance of using a mix of LOTS and HOTS questions to engage students, promote critical thinking, and accommodate different learning styles. Hattie and Timperley (2007), and Hill & Metcalf (2008) highlight the importance of effective questioning in promoting student learning and understanding. They suggest that using a mix of LOTS and HOTS questions can help achieve this goal. Grossman, Hammerness, & McDonald (2009) emphasized balancing LOTS and HOTS questions to enhance student learning and engagement. This balance ultimately leads to better learning outcomes and overall educational experiences.
 - 2) Sujariati, et al. (2016) recommend that teachers use consistent questioning strategies, repeating questions, emphasizing meaning, translating or mixing questions into Bahasa Indonesia, and being closer to students to understand their learning weaknesses. Translating English questions into a student's first language enhances comprehension (Genesee, et al., 2010), promotes equity and inclusion (Cummins, 2000), boosts confidence and engagement (Skutnab-Kangas, & Cummins, 2008), facilitates cognitive processing (Dewaele, 2018), and encourages multilingualism (Garcia, & Wei, 2014). This is especially beneficial for students developing their English skills or from non-English-speaking backgrounds. It also ensures equal access to the curriculum and encourages a more inclusive learning environment. This approach is particularly beneficial in multilingual and multicultural societies.
 - 3) The remaining 18.75% has no suggestion at all.
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Conclusions

This systematic review found 16 articles on teachers' use of LOTS-HOTS questioning. The studied articles were not limited to a single country. The results of these studies are quite revealing. A significant majority, 81.25%, of the research found that LOTS were more commonly used in educational settings than HOTS. This could be due to several factors, including the perceived difficulty of teaching and assessing HOTS, or the belief that LOTS are easier to construct. Large class sizes, limited instructional time, and diverse student populations may also pose challenges to implementing HOTS-promoting instructional strategies (Darling-Hammond, 2010). Teachers may struggle to engage all students in meaningful, higher-order thinking activities while adhering to curriculum and scheduling guidelines. Another plausible explanation is that many teachers may have received insufficient training in instructional strategies that promote HOTS. According to research, professional development programs that focus on strategies like inquiry-based

learning, problem-based learning, and collaborative learning can help teachers foster higher-order thinking in their classrooms (Guskey & Yoon, 2009). However, it is important to note that not all studies came to the same conclusion. A small but significant percentage of 6.25% discovered that teachers were still using HOTS in their questions. This suggests that, despite the general trend toward LOTS, there is still a dedicated group of educators who understand the value of HOTS and are committed to incorporating them into their teaching practices.

Lastly, 12.5% of the studies yielded dissimilar results, indicating that the relationship between LOTS and HOTS in educational settings is not a simple, one-size-fits-all issue. These studies may have focused on different educational levels, subject areas, or cultural contexts, which could have influenced the outcomes.

The studies discussed provide useful insights into the current state of educational practices, particularly the use of LOTS and HOTS. While the majority of research supports the prevalence of LOTS, a sizable minority emphasizes the continued use of HOTS in questioning, as well as the importance of taking into account a variety of factors when asking HOTS questions. Examining these studies from a global perspective allows us to gain a more nuanced understanding of the complexities of educational practice and the ongoing debate surrounding the use of LOTS and HOTS in questioning strategies. Considering the prior conclusions, the recommendation for additional research can be separated into two parts. First, since most of the studies revealed that teachers need training to successfully incorporate HOTS in their questioning strategically, further research would focus on the kinds and appropriateness of training programs for improving teachers' skills in implementing HOTS-based questions. Second, considering the studies of Rooney (2012), Ansori (2019), and Shalihin et al. (2019), there is a tendency that students may understand and incorporate HOTS questions in their engagement; further research would investigate other activities that develop HOTS for students. Nevertheless, this study offers helpful data for determining the feasibility of incorporating HOTS questions into qualifications that educate future educators.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The review employed data from openly available sources and previously published studies. Proper citations and acknowledgments were provided to all original authors and sources to respect intellectual property rights and avoid plagiarism. The researcher has no conflicts of interest related to this article.

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